

High-precision displacement sensor based on resonant cavities through an electronic interface based on Arduino

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Abstract

A novel stand-alone, high-precision, compact and cost-effective positioning sensor based on resonant cavities is described. It consists of two parts: the transducer based on radio frequency resonant cavities; and an electronic system that uses a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO), a mixer as phase detector, and an Arduino interface to find the voltage through which the VCO operates the transducer. The resonant frequency of the device is directly related to a voltage null in the mixer output signal, in such a way that its measurement allows to deduce the correct driving signal value. This value represents the complete system displacement.

Experimental tests have proven the effectiveness of the presented system in proposed displacement measurement tests performed in the range of micrometers.

Keywords: Micro- and nano-positioning sensor, resonant cavities, resonant frequency detector.

1. Introduction

Any kind of micro- or nano-technological application requires ultra-precision metrology and manufacturing. From the many ways of sensing displacement [1, 2, 3], and as it is clearly summarized in [1], due to the extreme breadth of position sensor technologies suitable for nanopositioning applications, it is extremely

difficult to make direct performance comparisons. Among all of sensors considered in [1] (resistive, piezoelectric and piezoresistive strain sensors, capacitive sensors, electrothermal sensors, eddy current sensors, linear variable displacement transformers, interferometers, and lineal encoders), it is concluded that
10 capacitive [4] and eddy-current sensors [5, 6] can be designed with subnanometer resolution in small range and low bandwidth. In general, to achieve high absolute accuracy over large range, the reference standard is the laser heterodyne interferometer [7, 8, 9]. Although laser interferometers are bulky and costly, the accuracy, stability and linearity exceed all other sensors. Linear encoders are
15 also used in similar applications to interferometers where absolute accuracy is the primary concern. Nevertheless, new methods of measuring displacement at very small scales keep being an open field of research with high technological interest. Due to the lack of cost effective sensors that provide both high-resolution and wide bandwidth, recent research has also considered the collaborative use
20 of multiple above measuring principles. In [10] a piezoelectric strain sensor and capacitive sensor are combined. Moreover, different solutions based on the use of new materials have been proposed, as magnetostrictive TbDyFe [11] or carbon nanotubes [12], for example. Recently, another approach involving the use of variable inductance planar coils has been proposed, with a nanometric displacement resolution [13]. In [14] another solution based on vertical stacked
25 two-dimensional atomic corrugated layer materials is suggested. On the other hand, a microactuator displacement is wirelessly controlled based on resonant frequency tracking and using Vector Network Analyzer in [15, 16].

In our previous works, an RF resonant cavity-based displacement transducer
30 was presented [17]. The electromagnetic variations caused by the geometry change of the resonant cavities allow to measure small displacements. It was demonstrated that subnanometric displacements can easily be detected using this principle.

Though a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) could be used to measure those
35 electromagnetic variations, specifically to determine the resonant frequency from the transmission or reflection parameters obtained from the system by sweeping

the excitation frequency, this method is very expensive and does not provide a stand-alone solution of the measurement system since it depends on an external measuring device. In order to replace the VNA with minimum loss of resolution and accuracy, the authors have proposed different solutions: in [18] an electronic interface based on low pass filters, power detectors and low noise amplifier was used, whereas in [19], a reliable method for determining resonant frequencies involving a mixer as a phase detector was described.

In this work, based on those ideas, a new accurate, integrated and cost effective electronic interface solution is presented. It is based on the widespread low cost hardware/software platform Arduino [20]. This is customized and used together with the displacement transducer presented in [17] in order to find the resonant frequency resulting on account of the change in the geometry of the resonant cavities due to the displacement.

The system is composed of a Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO) coupled to a mixer using as phase detector through a controller (the Arduino) that finds the tune voltage of the VCO producing the phase-null, which appears at the resonance condition. So, the measuring system translates the resonant phase into a DC voltage, which is proportional to the displacement and can be directly measured.

The paper is organized as follows: The second section describes the transducer used and its principle of operation. Next, section III summarizes the electronic interface used to measure the transducer's response. The complete stand-alone displacement sensor implementation and the obtained experimental results are shown in section IV. Finally, conclusions make up the last section.

2. Transducer's description and principle of operation

Figure 1 shows the general schematic of the laboratory prototype displacement sensor, made of copper, which comprises two resonant cavities whose dimensions change in opposite directions as a function of displacement. Therefore, the variations of the electromagnetic characteristics of the cavities caused

by this geometry change allows for the measurement of the displacement [17]. The brown colored part, labeled 2, is the body of the transducer. The central part, 1, is the moving part, it is connected to the transmission rod, which is moved by a micrometer that produces position changes. The movement of this
70 part modifies the geometry of the resonant cavities, which are formed between this part and the body of the transducer (they are identified by 3). A resonant cavity behaves similarly to an RLC circuit where its resonant frequency is proportional to $1/\sqrt{LC}$. In the cavity, the equivalent L remains constant while the equivalent C changes with the variable gap, much in the way a parallel plate
75 capacitor does (proportional to $1/d$ with d the distance between plates). In this way, globally the resonant frequency changes, in each cavity of the sensor, proportionally to the square root of the gap change.

Figure 1: The image and general scheme of the laboratory prototype sensor. The micrometer's movement is transmitted to the central part through the rod. The movement of the central part changes the cavities' geometry, and hence, their resonant frequency.

Let g be the gap, r_1 the radius of the gap region, r_2 the outer radius of the cavity and l its length (see Figure 1) and c the speed of light, the resonant
80 frequency, f , at the central position is

$$f = \frac{c\sqrt{2g}}{2\pi r_1 \sqrt{l \log_{10}\left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right)}}. \quad (1)$$

The absolute variation of frequency with the displacement, Δf , may be found

Figure 2: Characterization of the resonance frequency of one cavity of the transducer as a function of the displacement.

by taking a logarithmic derivative of the central frequency expression

$$\frac{\Delta f}{f} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta g}{g} - \frac{\Delta l}{l} \right). \quad (2)$$

In order to have a high sensitivity, the g gap dimension will be much smaller than the total cavity length, and therefore, the first term inside the parentheses
85 dominates.

As it had been experimentally demonstrated in [17], if the transmission rod is displaced in a controlled way by means of a micrometer head and the frequency response is registered using an RF network analyzer, the transducer characterization shown in Figure 2 is obtained. Each individual cavity in the
90 prototype changes its frequency with displacement from 280 MHz to 730 MHz approximately. As it is described in more detail in [17], although one cavity would be enough to sense displacement, using two cavities in differential mode doubles the sensitivity of the device and compensates slight nonlinearities in

Figure 3: Magnitude and phase response form of a typical resonant system. Different colors show several damping factors response.

the extreme positions and possible inaccuracies due to thermal expansion of the
 95 cavities. Both cavities undergo the same temperature changes and thus, the
 expansion effects cancel each other if used in differential mode, in such a way
 that the transducer is insensitive to temperature changes. It is remarkable the
 very high sensitivity of the device, whose response changes as much as 1.125
 MHz in frequency for each micrometer (or 2.25 MHz if we use two cavities).

100 3. Resonant frequency measurement basis and electronic interface description

The theoretical magnitude and phase response of a typical resonant system
 is shown in Figure 3, where a phase displacement of 180° is observed in the
 transmission coefficient around the resonance, being 90° for frequencies below
 105 the resonance, -90° for frequencies above the resonance and 0° at the resonance

Figure 4: Schematic of the set-up configuration in order to use a mixer as a phase detector.

frequency independently of the resonant frequency or damping factor absolute values.

As in [19] is detailed, if a signal that perturbrates the resonator is also split with 90° of phase difference, and both signals are mixed (see Figure 4), the
 110 output DC signal after the low pass filter, becomes:

$$V_{DC} = V_{off} + V_{in}V_{90} \cos(\Delta\phi), \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\phi = \phi_{in} + \phi_{90} + \phi_e$, and ϕ_{in} is the phase due to the resonator, ϕ_{90} is the shifted signal's phase (90°), and ϕ_e is the mixer-induced phase shift. V_{off} is the offset voltage error, which is a function of the power feeding the mixer, and V_{in} and V_{90} are signal amplitudes once the resonator and shifter are used.
 115 Note that an attenuator is used in the second channel to compensate the losses of the resonator and hence, to equilibrate the power in both branches.

In order to confirm this basis, a test has been implemented and with the transducer shown in previous section. The generator exciting the resonator shown in Figure 4, is replaced by a voltage controlled oscillator (ZX95-540-S+,
 120 390-540 Mhz, Mini-Circuits) that is driven by Arduino microcontroller (Arduino Uno). The signal generated is amplified (ZX60-6013E-S+, 20-6000 MHz, Mini-Circuits) in order to excite the resonator (one of the transducers cavities), and on the other hand, it is also dephased 90° (ZX109-2-5-S+, 330-580 MHz, Mini-circuits). The Arduino measures the DC signal generated by a mixer (ZEM

Figure 5: Mixer output measured when the VCO is driven by Arduino for a fixed specific position.

125 2B+, 10-1000 MHz, Mini-Circuits). Figure 5 shows the DC output of the mixer when one of the cavities of the sensor described in the previous section is used as resonant system. The combined effect of phase and amplitude of the transmission coefficient for a broad range of frequencies when the transducer is in a specific position is shown as example. As it can be concluded, near the resonance

130 the mixer brings DC values, negative for frequencies below the resonance frequency and positive for higher ones, and a DC null occurs precisely when both signals differ by -90° , (i.e. when the resonator is excited with the resonant frequency). From this result, it is possible to determine the resonant frequency by measuring the voltage at the output of the filter and finding the null.

135 **4. Complete stand-alone displacement sensor system implementation**
and experimental results

As it has been explained above, in order to determine the displacement, the purpose of the electronic interface system is to find the frequency at which the mixer DC value is null for each position. Though the DC null could be found for both resonant cavities in the transducer, in this work only one cavity of the transducer is used to verify the measurement technique. The use of both
140 cavities implies duplicating all the RF discrete elements but it does not provide contribution in methodology. The process implemented is summarized below.

In order to assign the first frequency interval to find the null, equidistant
145 voltage values are sent to the VCO through the Arduino. The distance of those intervals has been determined taking into account that at least one positive and another negative value must exist. By observing the transducer response (see Figure 5, blue points), we can conclude that 10 MHz frequency intervals are enough to find positive and negative values.

Once initial values are determined (the respective VCO tune values of those
150 positive and negative readings), the bisection method is executed and when it converges, that means that the VCO is driving the system at the resonant frequency. The measurement of this voltage determines the resonant frequency and hence, the displacement. In order to verify the used method, a spectrum analyzer (E4440A, Agilent) and displacement capacitive sensor (4810, AD Technologies) are added to the system.

The number of iterations of the bisection method must be equal to the number of resolution bits of the DAC to achieve the maximum precision. In order to improve the complete system precision, a 16-bit analog to digital converter
160 (ADS1115, Adafruit) and a 20-bit digital to analog converter (DAC1220 Texas Instruments) have been added. Those two components allow to measure the DC signal, and the voltage driving the VCO respectively. The communication between the Arduino and the ADC is implemented through the I2C protocol, whereas the DAC is controlled by the SPI protocol. Figure 6 shows the complete

Figure 6: A schematic and a photograph of the complete system. The Arduino tunes de VCO and executes the bisection algorithm in order to find the mixer null, and hence, the transducer resonant frequency.

165 schematic and photograph of the system.

With regards to the attainable precision, using the proposed system, as a 20 bits digital-to-analog converter has been used to tune the VCO, the oscillator control signal could be controlled within $5 \mu\text{V}$. This, in turn, corresponds to 220 Hz, and taking into account the transducer precision shown in Figure 2, it

170 results in an excellent maximum theoretical resolution of 0.2 nm for the proposed
sensor. Moreover, we have experimentally concluded that even if the VCO can
be controlled within 5 μV , the oscillator frequency stability and the noise added
by the phase detector employed in the system would be the key limiting factors in
those measurements. When needed, using low noise amplification prior to phase
175 detection could reduce this last contribution. On the other hand, the frequency
stability, or the degree to which the VCO is able for producing the frequency
value throughout the measurement time, can be significantly improved by using
standard phase-locked techniques (PLL). And, the fundamental noise floor of
this method would be limited in practice by the stability of the reference source.

180 The complete system response is shown in Figure 7. The rod is displaced by
means of using the micrometer at intervals of around 5 μm . This displacement
is transmitted, and when the system detects a resonance frequency change, it
executes the bisection method finding the null. When the process converges the
system measures the final voltage tuning the VCO. In the upper part of Figure
185 7, this voltage is represented as a function of displacement. Moreover, a resonant
frequency measured by the spectrum analyzer is represented in the lower part of
the same figure. The measurement range has been reduced from 400 μm to 150
 μm due to VCO operation range (390-540 MHz). This result exhibits an excellent
agreement between the DC signal coming from the electronic interface and the
190 actual frequency in the cavity measurable with the spectrum analyzer. This
clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed transducer plus electronic
interface as a standalone high precision sensor.

5. Conclusions

A novel stand-alone micro- and nanopositioning sensor has been described
195 and experimentally tested in this work. The system is based on a transducer
built using radio frequency resonant cavities, and a low cost electronic system
that uses a VCO, a mixer as phase detector, and an Arduino to find the null
in the mixer output signal. It has been experimentally demonstrated that the

Figure 7: Complete system response. In each position the method described is applied and the resulting voltage is measured and compared with the resonant frequency measured with the external spectrum analyzer.

transducer translates small position variations (nm) to large resonant frequency
 200 variations (kHz), and this frequency changes can be easily measured by the
 electronic interface as voltage variations (V).

Although in this prototype micrometer precision limits minimum displace-
 ments, the results show that the theoretical complete sensor sensitivity is $5 \mu V$.
 This, in turn, corresponds to 220 Hz, and taking into account the transducer
 205 precision shown in Figure 2, it results in an excellent maximum resolution of
 0.2 nm for the proposed sensor.

As a general conclusion, it can be stated that the proposed complete system,
 comprising the resonant cavities plus the electronic interface, constitute a cost-
 effective, stand-alone and accurate displacement sensor, useful in micro and
 210 nano displacement applications.

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